

Essey

Mission-Oriented Reconstruction of Ukraine

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Abstract

Russia's full-scale invasion of Ukraine has caused economic destruction unprecedented in recent European history. In addition to damaging infrastructure, housing, and energy systems, the war has revealed structural weaknesses, including deindustrialization, institutional fragility, and reliance on resource oriented exports. This paper contends that Ukraine's reconstruction is not only about restoring assets but opportunity for state-building, economic transformation, and long-term security.

Drawing on development economics and comparative post-conflict experiences, this essay contrasts successful reconstruction cases, such as post-war Western Europe and South Korea, with failures in Syria, Afghanistan, and South Vietnam. It highlights the importance of state capacity, institutional coordination, and development-oriented finance in converting external assistance into lasting growth. The paper proposes a mission-driven National Development Bank to address this challenge, as an "investor of first resort". Ukraine's post-war recovery should focus on mobilizing long-term capital, supporting industrial upgrading, and matching with European integration and security objectives.

Contents

1	Introduction	3
2	Ukraine’s Structural Vulnerability: Three Decades of Deindustrialization (1991–2022)	4
3	Identifying the Nature and Scale of Reconstruction Needs	7
4	Reconstruction, Economic Development, and Post-Conflict Stability	8
5	Theoretical Foundations of Restarting the Development Model	11
6	Conclusion	13
7	Disclosure	15
A	Annex	18

1 Introduction

Russia’s full-scale invasion of Ukraine has caused economic damage not seen in recent European conflicts. Along with widespread destruction of energy and industrial sites, the war has created a humanitarian crisis affecting over 2.5 million households and displacing nearly 11 million people. The Fourth Rapid Damage and Needs Assessment (World Bank, 2025) puts the total reconstruction cost at US\$524 billion, with direct damage to housing and transport infrastructure alone exceeding US\$90 billion.

The extent of the damage poses a major challenge for policymakers. They must create a reconstruction plan that supports both rebuilding and long-term economic change. Here, post-war reconstruction goes beyond just humanitarian aid or welfare. It is key to building a resilient state. Lessons from other post-conflict situations show that lasting economic recovery depends on political stability, strong state institutions, and secure sovereignty.

There is ongoing debate in economic research about the best ways to deliver post-conflict aid. The cases of Syria under Assad and South Vietnam show that if reconstruction does not lead to lasting growth, it leading to instability or collapse. In contrast, Western Europe’s recovery after 1945 shows that success relied on strong market institutions, like property rights and courts, along with state-led development finance (Evans, 1995; Luna-Martínez & Vicente, 2012). National Development Banks, especially West Germany’s KfW, were important by using public guarantees and private capital to fund industrial modernization and help stabilize politics during times of international tension (Mazzucato, 2023).

Current discussions of a “Ukrainian Marshall Plan” often overlook the need for strong institutions and the broader international context of reconstruction. While Ukraine had a large industrial base in the early 1990s, its post-Soviet years saw factories close, money leave the country, and weak coordination among institutions. History shows that countries at key geopolitical moments face big risks: those that rebuild their industries and institutions strengthen their sovereignty, while those that do not may become dependent or sidelined in the global system (Acemoglu & Robinson, 2012).

This paper explores whether a mission-driven National Development Bank, seen as an “investor of first resort” (Mazzucato, 2023), could help solve these structural problems. Drawing on Peter Evans’ concept of embedded autonomy (Evans, 1995) and other development theories, the study examines when a national development bank can act as an effective and independent institution. Such a bank could attract long-term investment, support economic change, and strengthen Ukraine’s role in Europe and the world by linking reconstruction to long-term integration and security goals.

2 Ukraine's Structural Vulnerability: Three Decades of Deindustrialization (1991–2022)

Ukraine faced the current conflict after thirty years of steady deindustrialization. When it became independent, the country had many features associated with successful late industrialization, such as a large and varied industrial base, advanced energy generation, including nuclear power, accessible education, strong science, fertile farmland, and valuable natural resources. In 1991, machine-building made up about 31 percent of all industrial production. Overall, Ukraine had a strong foundation for long-term economic growth.

However, government was not ready at an institutional level to handle the shift from a planned economy to a market system. As noted by (Kindzerskyi, 2021), Ukraine began reforms without the necessary administrative skills or experience to ensure a smooth transition. As a result, the country went through one of the longest and most severe periods of deindustrialization worldwide. The breakdown of Soviet-era production links caused a sharp drop in output, with industrial value-added falling by almost 70 percent by 1998. In advanced economies, deindustrialization usually means a move to high-productivity services and technology. Ukraine's decline happened too early, before its productivity and income matched those of developed countries.

This result was tied to the use of neoliberal economic reforms based on the Washington Consensus. In Ukraine, these reforms kept poverty high, while the state's role in medicine, education, and science shrank. (Schaefer & Johnson, 1998) found that in most countries adopted Washington Consensus reforms, economic conditions remained the same or worse. Policies such as rapid privatization, deregulation, fiscal austerity, and trade liberalization were implemented even though the country's institutions were not ready for them. Instead of encouraging competition and innovation, these changes led to social and economic instability. Opening markets to foreign goods and a stronger currency hurt local producers. Instead, the country shifted to exporting resources.

At the same time, Ukraine remains one of the resource-oriented countries that has failed to create its own national reserve fund. Economic calculations point to enormous lost opportunities. Given that the profitability of raw material exports often exceeds 50%, the introduction of even moderate export tariffs could radically change the financial landscape. This capital could become the foundation for a radical structural restructuring of the economy, financing programs for deep processing of products and creating high added value.

Parasitism on natural resources has established a stable corruption-resource model in Ukraine. Export flows have become convenient tools for extracting financial rent, which, in turn, has given rise to a specific class of "rent-oriented" elites. Instead of strategically planning the future of the state, these elites are focused on seizing and maintaining control

over raw material flows, protecting their monopolies from competitors, investing profits in the purchase of new political preferences, and simultaneously transferring capital offshore. The consequences are catastrophic. According to tax audit data, Ukraine has consistently been among the world's top ten leaders in terms of capital outflow over the past 30 years. The total amount of funds withdrawn is estimated at \$200 billion.

The failed move to a market economy also caused a long social crisis. Many skilled professionals lost job opportunities in Ukraine and chose to move abroad, leading to a steady brain drain and weakening the country's human capital. Population dropped from about 52 million in 1991 to around 45 million by early 2014, a loss of over 7 million people due to both natural decrease and migration (Bureau, 2014). This ongoing population decline is due to low birth rates and people leaving because of economic hardship, insecurity, and higher mortality. As a result, Ukraine lost important skills and saw its workforce shrink. This demographic decline reduces the number of skilled workers and weakens social structures, leaving many people marginalized and disempowered.

The Ukrainian government's efforts to develop industrial policy faced both internal and external challenges. At home, industrial policy became unpopular because it was associated with corruption and oligarchic control (Gerasymchuk, 2018). Abroad, steps to support local producers, such as localization rules, public procurement preferences, or "Buy Ukrainian" laws, met strong opposition from partners. These actions were criticized as breaking free trade rules and Ukraine's agreements with the WTO, EU. Along with ongoing underinvestment in science, infrastructure, and export financing, these issues made it hard for the state to lead structural change.

The 2008 global financial crisis showed how weak Ukraine's growth model was. When credit markets collapsed, it became clear that Ukraine depended heavily on exporting raw materials, especially low-value metals and basic goods. Trade financing interest rates were often above 18 percent, and there was little state support for export financing. As a result, many value-added industries could not modernize. From 2007 to 2021, car production dropped by 98%, bus production by 90%, and tractor production by 77%. These changes increased regional inequality and frustration among workers and policymakers.

At the same time, Ukraine became more reliant on the Russian market for its manufactured exports. By 2008, Russia was the biggest buyer of Ukrainian industrial goods (Milakovskiy & Vlasiuk, 2023). This dependence made Ukraine economically vulnerable, and Russia later took advantage of it. They imposed high tariffs on key exports when Ukraine started integration negotiations with the European Union in 2011. These actions hit eastern regions the hardest, especially Donetsk Oblast, where exports dropped by 27 percent between 2011 and 2013. Industries like railcar manufacturing, a key part of Ukraine's machine-building sector, suffered greatly. This economic shock led to more regional instability and made Eastern part of Ukraine vulnerable to intervention, which happened in 2014.

From 2014 to 2021, Ukraine's economy became more stable but did not grow. Manufacturing kept shrinking as a part of GDP. Even though trade with the European Union increased overall, the quality of exports got worse. Fewer manufactured goods were sent to the EU, and machine-building focused more on low-value parts instead of finished products (Milakovsky & Vlasiuk, 2023).

A similar pattern emerged with the introduction of EU climate-related trade regulations. The Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism aims to prevent carbon leakage by imposing tariffs on emission-intensive imports such as steel, cement, and fertilizers. Although the policy serves a legitimate environmental objective, it poses a serious challenge for Ukraine's industrial sector. According to (GMK Center, 2024), Ukrainian production remains significantly more energy-intensive than that of EU member states, reflecting decades of underinvestment in modernization rather than regulatory neglect. As a result, the competitiveness of Ukrainian exports dropped at a critical moment.

Another sign of deindustrialization was the sharp rise in ferrous scrap exports. Ferrous scrap serves as an essential additive in steel production from iron ore. In the electrometallurgical sector, which is the most environmentally sustainable, ferrous scrap is the primary raw material, accounting for over 90 percent of steel production.

After exporting fewer than 300,000 tons of scrap metal in 2013, Ukraine increased its exports to over 920,000 tons in 2014 and more than 1.2 million tons in 2015, with most shipments directed to Turkish steel producers (Bureau of International Recycling, 2016).

This example of carbon arbitrage, in which emissions-intensive production stages are externalized through export reclassification and offshore processing. Climate-related trade regulations may encourage the relocation of value-added activities. This dynamic reinforces industrial hollowing-out in countries with limited access to green finance and modernization capital.

In 2020, Ukraine's parliament tried to strengthen support for the struggling machine-building sector. The Localization Law required public authorities to use more Ukrainian-made parts in vehicles over time. Policy aimed to stabilize domestic manufacturing and preserve industrial employment. A last-minute intervention by the EU Mission in Ukraine secured exemptions for European and US suppliers, sharply reducing the law's capacity to stimulate domestic value chains.

Dependency theory rather describes Ukraine as a peripheral country that developed on the edges of the global economy. Its main role was to provide resources and cheap labor for core countries. However, after the war began, this path is no longer possible. A weak state model only increases the risk of future intervention. To stop further depopulation, Ukraine needs to raise income levels to match those in Eastern Europe as soon as possible. This will take strong coordination and commitment from European investors and institutions, with cooperation between Ukrainian businesses and the government.

3 Identifying the Nature and Scale of Reconstruction Needs

Full-scale aggression caused to unprecedented damage on the Ukrainian state in the 21st century, affecting productive assets and civilian infrastructure. Energy systems, industrial facilities, transport networks, and housing stock have been systematically targeted. Based on World Bank evaluation, total cost of reconstruction exceeds USD 500 billion (World Bank, 2025). Overview of damages, needs, and sectoral impacts is provided in Table 1, with losses continuing to accumulate as hostilities persist. The war in Ukraine is one of the most destructive conflicts of recent decades and creates reconstruction challenges of exceptional scale and complexity.

In addition to physical destruction, the war has produced an intense humanitarian and demographic crisis. International Organization for Migration report that, 4.6 million people internally displaced inside Ukraine, while an additional 6.7 million Ukrainians remain abroad. The poverty rate increased sharply between 2021 and 2023, rising from 20.6% to 35.5%. The most vulnerable groups as households with children, large families, refugees, and persons with disabilities, have been affected first and most severely. 15% of the population lacks sufficient food security, showing a loss of purchasing power amid high inflation and declining real incomes.

Disruption of the labor market remains a main barrier to social recovery. Ukraine's labor force has decreased due to displacement, emigration, mobilization, and war-related injuries. Reintegration into the labor market is challenging for vulnerable groups, underscoring the need for active labor market policies, retraining programs and inclusive employment mechanisms. Demographic shifts driven by younger generations' migration have increased the proportion of pensioners, placing additional strain on the social protection system.

The housing sector is one of the most acute areas of fragility. Approximately 13% of Ukraine's total housing stock has been damaged or destroyed, affecting over 2.5 million households and resulting in estimated losses of USD 57.6 billion. The impact is especially severe in urban areas. Nearly two-thirds of the population resides in multi-family buildings that account for most damaged units. Circumstances of social inequality and complicate resettlement. Highlighted the need for reconstruction strategies that integrate housing recovery with labor market access and municipal infrastructure planning.

Monitoring missions by the International Atomic Energy Agency between 1 and 12 December 2025 confirmed that nuclear safety at three nuclear power plants remains operating under constant threat. Repeated disruptions in the power grid have caused voltage drop and temporary shutdowns at the Khmelnytskyi, Rivne, and South Ukraine nuclear power plants. Reactor units were required to operate at reduced capacity to stabilize the grid and prevent equipment damage. The occupation of the Zaporizhzhia Nuclear

Power Plant lead to dangerous periods of shutdown external power supply (International Atomic Energy Agency, 2024).

Beyond nuclear safety concerns, large-scale strikes on energy generation and distribution networks have resulted in economic and humanitarian costs. Missile and drone attacks target thermal power plants and renewable energy. That's include destruction of the Kakhovka Dam and repeated strikes on the Dnipro Hydroelectric Station. Ukraine's overall electricity generation capacity is currently estimated at roughly 30 percent of its pre-war level (International Atomic Energy Agency, 2024). Since February 2022, direct damage to Ukraine's energy infrastructure is estimated at approximately USD 14.8 billion (World Bank, 2025). Attacks concentrated during winter months, evince a deliberate strategy to exploit seasonal vulnerabilities by disrupting heating, water supply, sanitation, and healthcare services. Reduced energy availability amplifies economic losses across all sectors and affects vulnerable groups, including internally displaced persons and the elderly. Therefore, restoring the energy system is a technical challenge and fundamental prerequisite for reestablishing basic economic functionality, social stability, and national security.

By the end of 2024, real GDP remained at only 78% of its 2021 level, with growth projected to slow further due to labor shortages, energy restrictions, and ongoing security risks. Fiscal pressures are similarly acute: defense spending reached 32% of GDP in 2023, resulting in a budget deficit (excluding grants) of 26% and requiring external financing of nearly USD 40 billion in 2025 alone. Poverty rates have risen sharply, while workforce depletion from mobilization and emigration has reduced productive capacity by an estimated 25% .

Dynamics indicate that Ukraine's reconstruction challenge extends beyond physical rebuilding. The metallurgy and production sectors, including salt mines and gypsum factories, have been disrupted. Financial and institutional mechanisms for reconstruction has lead to structural economic transformation for reducing security risks. International support has to be complemented by domestic institutions that can mobilize long-term capital, restore state capacity, and anchor recovery within a durable progress trajectory.

4 Reconstruction, Economic Development, and Post-Conflict Stability

Recent research shows that economic development is key for decreasing the risk of renewed violence in post-conflict states, particularly those with social or ethnic divisions. Studies of Rwanda after the genocide demonstrate that combining macroeconomic stability with social inclusion foster lasting peace (Rwigeema, 2025). Recovery efforts there focused on reducing poverty, improving access to basic services, and using coordinated state-led

development to support social reintegration. National identity was built around shared economic goals rather than ethnic ties. This approach promoted stability as well as reduced the likelihood of new conflicts. The Rwandan example suggests that inclusive economic development as a means of sustaining peace.

To apply Rwanda's lessons to other post-conflict situations, it is important to distinguish between cases with deep internal ethnic divisions and those where such divisions are externally created or exaggerated. In Ukraine, the Russian government has cited alleged ethno-linguistic conflict since 2013 to justify its actions. However, research shows that language and regional identity in Ukraine do not cause ongoing ethnic conflict. Surveys from the Harvard Ukrainian Research Institute (2024) indicate that language preference does not predict disloyalty or intergroup hostility. This differs from the deep ethnic divisions present in Rwanda before the genocide.

Nevertheless, Ukraine faces growing domestic divisions. That including tensions between the military and those who can legally avoid or have managed to avoid mobilization, as well as between those who remained in Ukraine and those who left during the war. These divisions go beyond social or moral issues and include significant economic and institutional challenges. The return of refugees, reintegration of veterans, and restoration of intergroup trust will depend on the course of post-war development. A comprehensive economic recovery strategy that focuses on security, employment, and equity is essential for restoring social unity and securing peace in Ukraine.

Rebuilding the economy helps nations stand strong against outside challenges. Historical evidence from the Cold War shows that developed economies helped post-conflict states resist external threats. The different outcomes of South Korea and South Vietnam after the ideological division of East Asia illustrate this point. Although both countries received substantial external assistance, their courses diverged. As (Gray, 2013) notes, South Vietnam sometimes received as much or more aid than South Korea, but only South Korea converted this support into sustained economic growth and political stability.

The different outcomes in South Korea and South Vietnam were not determined by the amount of aid alone. Key differences included state capacity, institutional strength, and economic planning. South Korea implemented effective post-war administration, launched early land reforms and involved broad segments of the population in national development. These actions enhanced state legitimacy and supported a transition to industrialization and export-led growth. In contrast, South Vietnam faced weak governance. Focused on short-term military goals limited the effective use of aid for sustainable economic transformation. Economic fragility increased political instability despite ongoing external support. This comparison highlights the need for post-conflict reconstruction to prioritize institution-building that can turn external resources into lasting economic growth and peace.

The Syrian conflict presents a contrasting example, showing how inadequate reconstruction can accelerate the decline of state structures. Contemporary conflicts often follow a three-stage trajectory:

1. An initial phase of domestic uprising driven by socio-economic grievances;
2. A second phase characterised by internationalisation and proxy warfare;
3. A final phase of fragmentation and regime collapse.

In Syria, reconstruction policies during the transition from active conflict to regime consolidation focused narrowly on elite interests. As (Hourani, 2016) documents, investment strategies prioritized real estate development and commercial returns for those close to the regime. Social infrastructure and broad-based economic recovery were neglected. External allies, motivated by their own regional interests, provided limited support for genuine reconstruction beyond securing their own positions. Under sanctions and economic isolation, the lack of substantive rebuilding further eroded social cohesion and state legitimacy, leading to illicit economic activity. At last regime lost its legitimacy among its own security forces. This erosion of inner unity helps explain the rapid collapse of authority once external pressure intensified.

A similar dynamic occurred in Afghanistan in 2021. Afghan state suffered from deep institutional weaknesses, widespread corruption, and limited public trust. The government's authority was concentrated in urban centers, while much of the countryside remained outside state control. The Afghan National Security Forces, though large and well-equipped, lacked confidence in political leadership. The withdrawal of international troops revealed deficiencies, despite two decades of military and financial assistance.

This three-stage trajectory is already evident in Ukraine. The first phase was the hybrid war in Donbas (2014–2021), during which the Kremlin set the conflict's framework and justified its actions internally. The second phase is the ongoing full-scale war, focused on immediate objectives, with a pause expected. The third phase will likely involve a major offensive aimed: weakening Ukraine's military and asserting control over the country. The conflict fits the concept of a war of attrition, as described by (Svechin, 1992), involving incremental advances and significant destruction. This three-stage conflict will likely continue until one side is completely exhausted.

The three-phase structure includes pauses in hostilities intended to provoke political crises in the adversary and weaken them without direct conflict. During these periods, competing development models emerge. Russia expects to recover through a militarized Keynesian approach and anticipates that the pause will reduce Ukraine's population and economic capacity. Historical precedent shows that Ukraine must accelerate its development to achieve greater progress. Only a strong economy and strategic defense

resource allocation can maintain stability during these pauses and potentially prevent the third phase of the conflict.

Post-conflict states with fragile economies are much more vulnerable to renewed violence, external intervention, or fragmentation. Therefore, reconstruction should be seen not just as aid or recovery, but as the essential basis for long-term resilience.

5 Theoretical Foundations of Restarting the Development Model

Ideological foundations for an effective reconstruction strategy must take into account historical experiences of economic development and post-war reconstruction. Ukraine's economic failures are included in discussions about future reconstruction. The literature debates the most effective mechanisms for distributing financial assistance in post-war contexts. Historical experience supports the importance of institutional design in this process. Reconstruction efforts in Iraq and Afghanistan relied heavily on direct grants and external budgetary support and failed to generate sustainable economic growth (SIGAR, 2021; World Bank, 2017). More broadly, Moyo (2009) argues that post-conflict states often operate under weak institutional conditions. In such environments, grant transfers may reinforce corruption, rent-seeking behavior, and political capture rather than promote long-term development.

How do states respond to such economic self-destruction? Those patterns are common in states lacking experience of historic self-organization. A state that views the economy as a source of rents for elites (Evans, 1995) termed "predatory behavior". It is the opposite of what is requested for development-coordinated investment. Strategic coherence and internal government coordination are essential. To address this, Peter Evans offers a framework to overcome institutional weaknesses called "embedded autonomy". Case studies in South Korea, Brazil, and India, Evans shows that industrial upgrading is more likely, when state agencies are insulated from political interference but embedded in productive networks. Evans named two features of successful developmental: autonomy and embeddedness. Autonomy refers to the capacity of state agencies to follow long-term development goals on the one hand. On the other hand, restrict private interests such as oligarchs, clientelist networks, or short-term political pressures. Embeddedness refers to institutionalized links between the state, private firms, and society that enable information exchange, trust, and coordinated action. Model of interaction is required to satisfy this concept and avoid "predatory behavior". Institutional solution is organizations that are relatively distant from political power and private interests. National development banks can perform this role by functioning as the "islands of efficiency" that Evans describes. These enclaves are public agencies that operate within weak in-

stitutional environments. They remain out of short-term political cycles while applying clear financing rules, professional standards, and policy conditionality. Meanwhile, it is embedded in the national economy through close relationships with domestic firms, industries, and public authorities.

Nationally oriented institutions design instruments that reflect the specific characteristics and constraints of the domestic economy. Western Europe after 1945 followed this recovery trajectory. The Marshall Plan combined external financing with the creation of national institutions and the channeling of funds through the International Bank for Reconstruction and Development. This approach enabled rapid industrialization, modernization, and long-term growth, and remains the most successful example of post-war structural adjustment. Europe's recovery benefited from existing market institutions such as property rights and functioning legal systems. However, a key post-war achievement was the creation of a new financial architecture centered on national development banks. These institutions mobilized resources, combined government guarantees with private capital, and provided long-term financing for industry needs, infrastructure, and households. West Germany's Kreditanstalt für Wiederaufbau (KfW) institutional design serves as a model for development banks worldwide. This governance structure aligns investment decisions with national development strategies rather than with external donor priorities. In contrast, international development banks often focus on short-term projects and often rely on production inputs, expertise, and contractors from donor countries.

From an institutional perspective, effective recovery depends on resources mobilized and the way they are allocated. Inclusive institutions that foster investment, innovation, and inclusiveness are essential for sustainable growth. Mazzucato (2017, 2023)'s promote mission-oriented innovation policy provides and justifies the role of national development banks. Mission-oriented organization acts as a proactive "investors of first resort" that shape markets and guide structural transformation. It creates value chains and technological trajectories by taking on risks that private actors are unwilling to bear. For instance, innovation cycles take 15 to 20 years to mature, a horizon typically avoided by private finance. Development banks fill this gap by using a mix of long-term loans, equity stakes, guarantees, and green bonds. KfW Capital, acting as a venture capital investor in German and Europe, holds a portfolio of €2.5 billion.

Mission-oriented finance shifts from the neoclassical focus on "market fixing" to a proactive approach of "market shaping" and "market creating." This framework targets broader challenges such as climate change, demographic aging, and digital transformation. A good example is Germany's "Energiewende", where KfW played a central role in the transition to renewable energy. State investment is the main institutional vehicle for this approach. Mission-oriented theory emphasizes "embedded autonomy". A key organizational advantage of mission-oriented banks is their internal expertise. Unlike commercial banks, institutions such as Germany's KfW or Brazil's BNDES employ i

scientific, engineering, and sectoral knowledge. This allows them to evaluate projects with high uncertainty but long-term social and economic potential. Besides, “progressive conditions” are tied to public funding. Companies are expected to meet specific goals: making products affordable and accessible, matching climate targets, and reinvesting earnings into R&D for future growth.

Ukraine’s reconstruction should focus on the experience of countries that have developed amid ongoing geopolitical and existential threats. South Korea, Taiwan, Japan, and West Germany rebuilt and industrialized during the Cold War as frontline allies in a hostile environment. In these cases, economic policy was closely tied to national survival. Development is viewed as a security project.

Their economic models differed from the neoliberal paradigm. Countries relied on strong public institutions, development banks, and targeted industrial policies typical of the developmental state (Evans, 1995). They used protection of key sectors, capital controls, and state-directed credit to build domestic productive capacity and accelerate transformation. Firms received support but were disciplined through performance-based criteria, ensuring protection led to international competitiveness rather than stagnation (Wade, 1990).

The growth model allowed these countries to “raise the cost” of external intervention. Economic upgrading created the fiscal base, industrial depth, and technological capacities needed in case of militarization. In this way, economic “miracles” were gradually transformed into security assets. As their economies matured, these states took greater responsibility for their own defense and contributed to regional security, rather than remaining permanently dependent on external protection.

Ukraine now occupies a similar position on Europe’s eastern border. Its reconstruction should not be viewed as a simple return to normality. Like previous Cold War frontline states, it must rebuild while preparing for ongoing security challenges. Reconstruction policy should therefore prioritize state coordination, development finance, and strategic industry. The proposed National Development Bank of Ukraine serves as an instrument of institutional change. With professional management, a clear mission-oriented mandate, and a reinvestment-based financing model. Such an institution could counteract negative dynamics and generate positive spillover effects throughout the Ukrainian economy.

6 Conclusion

Ukrainian reconstruction differs significantly from typical post-conflict recovery. Ukraine faces not only physical rebuilding but also the reversal of decades-long deindustrialization amid existential threats. The crisis has revealed the shortcomings of the neoliberal “market-fixing” approach, which did not deliver the resilience needed for national defense and economic sovereignty.

A successful "Ukrainian Marshall Plan" must go beyond absorbing foreign aid. It needs institutions that can turn external capital into domestic productive capacity. The proposed National Development Bank is key to this effort. As an "investor of first resort." Mission-driven organisation fills the long-standing gap in "long and patient" capital for industrial modernization. Guided by embedded autonomy, it can operate effectively in line with national economic priorities.

Economic development becomes essential for security at critical geopolitical moments. Reconstruction has to build a high-value industrial base to reduce the risks of relapse intervention. This means prioritizing sectors that offer the technological capacity needed for economic growth and rapid military adaptation.

In conclusion, Ukraine's reconstruction must focus on structural transformation. Building strong state institutions and restoring industrial capacity are essential to move beyond its historical stagnation. Mission-oriented financial system necessary for a sovereign, resilient, and integrated Ukraine in the post-war European context.

7 Disclosure

Disclosure This material was prepared based on existing academic knowledge, synthesized with the author's vision. All findings, key points, perspectives, and descriptions were developed by the author. However, AI tools were used to enhance overall quality and efficiency.

Specifically:

NotebookLM was used for managing and navigating academic papers selected by the author.

Grammarly was used for partial translation and improving writing quality.

ChatGPT was used to assist in generating LaTeX code.

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A Annex

Table 1: *RDNA4 Data Snapshot*

Category	Indicator	Value
Overall	Direct damage	US\$176 billion
	Total recovery needs (10 years)	US\$524 billion
	2025 recovery and reconstruction priorities	US\$17.32 billion
	Secured financing (2025)	US\$7.4 billion
	Financing gap (2025)	US\$9.96 billion
Human Impacts	Refugees outside Ukraine (UN-HCR)	6.8 million
	Internally displaced persons (GoU)	4.6 million
	Women-only households below subsistence level	35%
	Families with ≥ 3 children living in poverty	84.7%
	Youth who lost housing (2024)	10%
	Domestic violence complaints (as of Oct 31, 2024)	168,256 cases
	Cost of increased unpaid child-care work (since Feb 2022)	US\$72.5 billion
	Population exposed to explosive remnants of war	6.1 million
Macroeconomic	External financing needs (2025)	US\$39.3 billion
	Real GDP (2024, 78%	
	Poverty rate (2023)	35.5%
Social Sectors	Housing stock damaged or destroyed	13%

Continued on next page

Category	Indicator	Value
	Affected households	>2.5 million
	Education infrastructure damaged or destroyed	>10%
	Health facilities damaged or destroyed	1,603 (16.2%)
	Children in hybrid schooling	741,000 (20%)
	Children fully remote	443,000 (12%)
	Social protection needs (IDPs, disabilities)	US\$2.3 billion
	Damaged social protection assets	200
	Damaged cultural and tourism assets	5,483
Productive Sectors	Settlements with extreme food security vulnerability (Donetska)	40%
	Settlements with extreme food security vulnerability (Kharkivska)	18%
	Irrigation repair needs (Khersonska oblast)	US\$1.85 billion
	Firms with >60% asset damage	25%
	Estimated credit losses	25% of pre-invasion loan portfolio
Infrastructure	Damage to district heating	>US\$2.5 billion
	Energy sector revenue losses	US\$72.3 billion
	Power sector revenue losses	US\$43.4 billion
	Railway infrastructure in damage-repair cycle	~30%
	Damage to public facilities and amenities	US\$977 million
	Damage to local mobility assets	US\$960 million

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Category	Indicator	Value
	Population lacking water and sanitation services	8.5 million
	Damage to telecom, digital, and media sectors	US\$2.21 billion
	Households without mobile access	12.2%
Cross-cutting	Increase in damage to forests (12 months)	14%
	Damaged forest and natural landscape area	698,845 ha
	Increase in emergency service responses since 2021	34.4%
	Average annual emergency interventions	479,055
	Damage to justice and public administration	US\$433 million
	Area contaminated with explosive ordnance	138,503 km ²
	Estimated cost of humanitarian mine action	US\$29.8 billion